

ETIOLOGY, PATHOGENESIS, ORIGIN AND PREVENTION OF VENTRICULAR
ARRHYTHMIA

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Abstract. *The heart is an organ that ensures the continuous movement of blood through the veins in the desired direction. It occurs due to the occurrence of impulses that stimulate the excitation and contraction of the myocardium.*

In a healthy person, different parts of the heart contract alternately, first the atria, and then the ventricles. The right atrium has a main source of rhythm called the sinus node.

In addition to the sinus node, other areas of the myocardium can generate impulses and create a rhythm. However, in a healthy person, they do not cause arrhythmias due to the normal functioning of the sinus node.

Key words: *Arrhythmia diagnosis, Arrhythmia treatment, Drug therapy, Non-drug methods, Arrhythmia complications, Arrhythmia prevention.*

ЭТИОЛОГИЯ, ПАТОГЕНЕЗ, ПРОИСХОЖДЕНИЕ И ПРОФИЛАКТИКА
ЖЕЛУДОЧКОВЫХ АРИТМИЙ.

Аннотация. *Сердце – орган, обеспечивающий непрерывное движение крови по венам в нужном направлении. Оно происходит за счет возникновения импульсов, стимулирующих возбуждение и сокращение миокарда.*

У здорового человека поочередно сокращаются разные отделы сердца: сначала предсердия, а затем желудочки. Правое предсердие имеет основной источник ритма, называемый синусовым узлом.

Помимо синусового узла, генерировать импульсы и создавать ритм могут и другие участки миокарда. Однако у здорового человека они не вызывают аритмий вследствие нормального функционирования синусового узла.

Ключевые слова: *Диагностика аритмии, Лечение аритмии, Медикаментозная терапия, Немедикаментозные методы, Осложнения аритмии, Профилактика аритмии.*

The urgency of the problem: The heart has conduction, that is, the ability to spread impulses throughout the myocardial tissue. This allows his cells to work harmoniously.

Arrhythmia - any disturbance in the electrical conductivity, frequency or regularity of the heart rhythm. Sometimes it has no symptoms, other times it manifests as palpitations, freezing or interruptions in heart activity. The patient may feel dizzy and even faint.

Research materials and methods: Depending on the heart rate, pathology is divided into types:

Tachyarrhythmia is an increase in heart rate of ninety or more beats per minute. Such a pulse can be a normal variant (physiological), that is, occurring during sports, excitement or fear, and pathological (increased heart rate at rest).

Bradyarrhythmia is a slowing of the heart rate to sixty beats per minute. in adults who are not athletes (or in children and adolescents, depending on their age, the heart rate slows down to 60-100 beats / min).

Atrial fibrillation is the most common type of disease in which the synchronous work of muscle fibers is disturbed due to their twitching or atrial fibrillation. That is, their contraction disappears, which is accompanied by disturbances in the functioning of the ventricles.

Extrasystole is a heart rhythm disorder in which the whole heart or its individual parts contract prematurely under the influence of a pathological impulse.

Paroxysmal tachycardia is a type of pathology characterized by attacks of heartbeat (paroxysm) with a heart rate from 140 to 220 or more / min. Paroxysms are caused by ectopic impulses that trigger the replacement of adequate sinus rhythm.

Depending on the location of the myocardial region, which is the source of the rhythm disturbance, they are divided into:

Supraventricular arrhythmias (the source of rhythm disturbances is localized in the atria or atrioventricular node).

Ventricular arrhythmias (the source of rhythm disturbance is located in the ventricles of the heart).

Sinus arrhythmias (the rhythm is disturbed due to improper functioning of the sinus node).

Causes of arrhythmia

Heart rhythm can be disturbed due to cardiac reasons or due to external factors.

Arrhythmias caused by heart failure:

Heart defects that appear in utero or during life.

Consequences of myocardial infarction.

Inflammation of the heart tissue (carditis).

GDP.

Myocarditis.

Neoplasms of the heart muscle.

Cardiomyopathies.

Heart failure.

Cardiac injuries and complications of cardiac surgery.

Long-term metabolic diseases, hypertension, alcoholism cause abnormalities in the structure of the myocardium.

External causes of pathology are considered to be conditions that cause rhythm disturbances, but do not cause disturbances in the structure of the heart muscle, for example, deviations in the electrolyte balance in diseases of the kidneys and adrenal glands.

Arrhythmia can occur as a result of stress, heavy physical activity or mental work, smoking, alcoholism, consumption of caffeinated drinks, as well as thyrotoxicosis, poisoning, fever, blood diseases, intoxication, etc.

Observed results: As a rule, arrhythmia is first detected by a therapist (in adults) or a pediatrician (in children). If the heart rhythm is abnormal, the patient should consult a cardiologist to determine the type of pathology and conduct a comprehensive examination of the cardiovascular system.

Summary: Electrocardiography (ECG) measures the electrical activity of the heart. The examination is very informative if it is carried out during a heart rhythm disorder. Then the doctor can determine the type of arrhythmia in the patient with 80% probability.

Daily ECG monitoring. If arrhythmia occurs almost every day, this study makes sense. It consists of a person wearing a small device on their body. It records three to twelve ECG tracks continuously for 1-3 days.

Event monitoring. The use of special tape recorders helps to understand whether the manifestations that disturb the patient are due to cardiac arrhythmias. The essence of the study is that the results are recorded only after the patient presses a certain button (when clinical manifestations appear).

REFERENCES

1. Sarkisova, V., Lapasova, Z., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). O. Rakhmanov INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE PELVIC WOMEN ORGANS.

2. Shernazarov I., Shernazarov F. Problems of translation of features related to the way of life of peoples //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. B1. – С. 80-83.
3. Jalalova, D., Axmedov, A., Kuryazov, A., & Shernazarov, F. (2022). COMBINED DENTAL AND EYE PATHOLOGY. Science and innovation, 1(8), 91-100.
4. Shernazarov F., Zuhridinovna J. D. Microcirculation disorders in the vascular system of the bulbar conjunctiva in the initial manifestations of cerebral blood supply deficiency //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. Special Issue 2. – С. 515-522.
5. Solovyova, Y., Prostyakova, N., Sharapova, D., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). The relevance of psychotic disorders in the acute period of a stroke. Science and innovation, 2(D12), 212-217.
6. Rotanov, A., Karshiyev, Z., Sharapova, D., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). Diagnosis of depressive and suicidal spectrum disorders in students of a secondary special education institution. Science and innovation, 2(D11), 309-315.
7. Shernazarov F. COMBINED DENTAL AND EYE PATHOLOGY //Science and Innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 8. – С. 91-100.
8. Madaminov M., Shernazarov F. Breast cancer detection methods, symptoms, causes, treatment //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D8. – С. 530-535.
9. Jalalova, D., Axmedov, A., Kuryazov, A., & Shernazarov, F. (2022). СОЧЕТАННАЯ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ И ГЛАЗНАЯ ПАТОЛОГИЯ. Science and innovation, 1(D8), 91-100.
10. Prostyakova, N., Solovyova, Y., Sharapova, D., & Shernazarov, F. (2023). Issues of professional ethics in the treatment and management of patients with late dementia. Science and innovation, 2(D12), 158-165.
11. Jalalova D., Raxmonov X., Shernazarov F. РОЛЬ С-РЕАКТИВНОГО БЕЛКА В ПАТОГЕНЕЗЕ СОСУДИСТЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ ОРГАНА ЗРЕНИЯ У БОЛЬНЫХ АРТЕРИАЛЬНОЙ ГИПЕРТЕНЗИЕЙ //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D8. – С. 114-121.
12. Pogosov S. et al. Psychogenetic properties of drug patients as risk factors for the formation of addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 186-191.
13. Sedenkova M. et al. The possibility of predicting the time of formation and development of alcohol dependence: the role of genetic risk, family weight and its level //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 173-178.

14. Farrukh S. ORGANIZATION OF DIGITALIZED MEDICINE AND HEALTH ACADEMY AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN MEDICINE //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. Special Issue 8. – C. 493-499.
15. Shamilov V. et al. Disorders of decision-making in the case of depression: clinical evaluation and correlation with eeg indicators //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 198-204.
16. Uskov A. et al. Modern methods of therapeutic fasting as a way to overcome the pharmacoresistance of mental pathology //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 179-185.
17. Prostyakova N. et al. Strategy for early diagnosis with cardiovascular diseaseisomatized mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 166-172.
18. Tahirova, J., Roziklov, N., Mamatkulova, F., & Shernazarov, F. (2022). Insomnia problem causes of sleep disorder, help measures at home. Science and innovation, 1(D8), 521-525.
19. Qizi T. J. I., Farrukh S. Treatment of myocardial infarction and first aid //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. D3. – C. 317-320.
20. Rotanov A. et al. Elderly epilepsy: neurophysiological aspects of non-psychotic mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 192-197.
21. Abdurakhmanov I., Shernazarov F. SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF TREATMENT OF CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS IN CHILDREN //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D10. – C. 164-168.
22. Tahirova J. et al. Neurose causes and mechanisms of development, symptoms, treatment, prevention //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. D8. – C. 515-520.
23. Tahirova J., Shernazarov F. Symptoms of hymoritis, treatment, methods of folk medicine, prevention //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. D8. – C. 983-990.
24. Shodiyeva D., Shernazarov F. Analysis of the compounds providing antihelmitic effects of chichorium intybus through fractionation. Science and innovation, 2 (D2), 64-70. – 2023.
25. Jalalova D., Normatova N., Shernazarov F. Genetic markers for the development of diabetic retinopathy //Science and Innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 8. – C. 919-923.
26. Abdukodirova S., Shernazarov F. SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS AND TREATMENT OF ACUTE OBSTRUCTIVE BRONCHITIS IN CHILDREN OF EARLY AGE //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 5-8.